

STUDIES IN GLASS SYSTEM. MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF
ALKALI SULPHATES DISSOLVED IN BORAX-GLASS
AND IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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In previous investigations, one of us (S.K.M.) has examined the change in diamagnetic susceptibility of salts dissolved in borax-glass by the Guoy balance and the more accurate torsion balance. It has been found that polar crystals such as alkali halides, sulphates, etc. show large increase of magnetic susceptibility in the dissolved state in the glass over their normal values. In the present paper, a comparison has been made between the diamagnetic susceptibilities of alkali sulphates in aqueous solution and in solution in borax-glass, the measurements being made by the torsion balance and in similar concentrations, as far as possible, subject to the restriction of solubility. The results in every case bear out the conclusion previously reached, that the diamagnetic susceptibility of the dissolved salt increases in solution in glass quite out of proportion with the small increases observed in aqueous solutions. The observed increase is difficult to explain, but a tentative explanation of the abnormal increase of the susceptibility is given.

Glass systems containing different polar salts in a state of solution have been studied in our laboratory in a series of investigations, in which mole-refraction, X-ray diffraction patterns and magnetic susceptibility of the dissolved salts have been examined. A rather remarkable result has been obtained from measurement of diamagnetic susceptibility of polar salts dissolved in boric oxide and borax-glasses (Majumdar and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 147; Majumdar and Banerjee, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1946, 18, 217; Majumdar, *Nature*, 1948, 161, 658). It has been found that the diamagnetic susceptibility of a salt like NaCl or Na₂SO₄, dissolved in borax-glass, as calculated from the additivity rule from the experimental value, is very much greater than its normal value. In the case of salts containing different cations, the discrepancy may in part be attributed to cationic exchange. But the explanation has to be sought elsewhere in cases of glass systems, like NaCl—Na₂B₄O₇ or Na₂SO₄—Na₂B₄O₇. As some of the former experiments referred to were carried out with Guoy balance, the accuracy of which is not great, it was thought desirable to extend the investigation with a more accurate instrument, namely the Magnetic torsion balance described by Krishnan and Banerjee (*Phil. Trans.*, 1935, A, 234, 265) and to measure side by side the change in susceptibility of these salts in aqueous solutions with the same instrument.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Samples.—Borax was recrystallised from conductivity water twice and completely dehydrated first in air-oven at 250° and then in a vacuum desiccator, until a small quantity taken in absolute alcohol did not colour anhydrous copper sulphate. The salts (Merck) were likewise recrystallised once and dehydrated. Lithium sulphate was prepared as described in a previous communication (Majumdar and Banerjee,

loc. cit.) by dissolving lithium carbonate in pure H_2SO_4 and twice recrystallising in a vacuum desiccator.*

Determination of Magnetic Susceptibility.—The magnetic susceptibility of the glass samples, as also of the pure constituents, was determined in a magnetic torsion balance (Krishnan and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) and modified later by Dutta (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1944, 18, 249). The glass pieces were attached to one end of a stout pyrex glass rod of suitable length, the other end being attached to the middle of a fine silver wire stretched horizontally between a graduated torsion head and a metal chuck. For solutions, a fine quartz wire was used instead of the silver wire. This increased the sensitivity of the instrument. For experiments with aqueous solutions, a piece of iron pyrite was attached to the end of the glass rod. The crystal of pyrite or the glass, as the case may be, was kept at a distance of 2 to 3 cm. away from the vertical sides of the flat pole pieces of a powerful electromagnet (about 2000 gauss), the gradient of the field being in the horizontal direction. The solid was attached in such a way that its basal plane was parallel to the direction of the uniform part of the field. In this way only the horizontal gradient of the field was effective in laterally displacing the solid, the wire being sufficiently stretched. The whole apparatus was enclosed in a case to protect it from dust and wind.

The glass was suspended in a liquid of known susceptibility and was viewed through a tele-microscope, so that one of the edges coincided with the scale marks. On switching the current, the solid moved laterally along the gradient in a direction away from the field, as all systems studied were diamagnetic. The torsion head was then slowly turned until the edge of the glass returned to its original position. The current was kept constant through regulating rheostats. The liquid was then replaced by another liquid, also of known susceptibility and the procedure repeated.

If κ_c be the volume susceptibility of the glass and κ_1 and κ_2 , that of the two liquids; A , the cross section of the glass piece; H_x , the field strength, the horizontal direction being the x -direction, and θ_1 and θ_2 , respectively the angles through which the torsion head is turned in the two liquids and R , the torsional constant of the wire,

$$\text{then} \quad \frac{1}{2} A \cdot H_x \cdot \frac{dH_x}{dx} (\kappa_c - \kappa_1) = R \cdot \theta_1 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \frac{1}{2} A \cdot H_x \cdot \frac{dH_x}{dx} (\kappa_c - \kappa_2) = R \cdot \theta_2 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Dividing (1) by (2)

$$\frac{\kappa_c - \kappa_1}{\kappa_c - \kappa_2} = \frac{\theta_1}{\theta_2} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

As all the quantities excepting κ_c are known, the latter may be calculated from the equation. The mass susceptibility (χ) was found out by dividing κ_c by the density of the

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sample determined in a hydrostatic balance. The liquids selected were Schering-Kahlbaum's pure pyridine ($\chi = -0.623 \times 10^{-6}$) and Merck's pure diethylaniline ($\chi = -0.835 \times 10^{-6}$), both freshly redistilled. It is clear that wider the difference in the values of χ of the two liquids, the larger will be the values of θ , and hence greater the sensitivity of the measurements. For aqueous solutions, conductivity water ($\chi = -0.720 \times 10^{-6}$) was first used with iron pyrite and then with the solutions.

The density of the solid pieces was determined by a hydrostatic balance, using nitrobenzene as the immersion liquid. The suspension was made with a single fibre of unspun silk to minimise the capillary rise of the liquid. The density of nitrobenzene, as also of the different aqueous solutions, was made in a specific gravity bottle in air simultaneously with the magnetic measurements.

Analysis of the Samples.—The samples of glass were analysed by taking a definite weight, dissolving it in hot water and acidifying with pure HCl. The sulphate was precipitated by BaCl₂ in the usual way and the precipitated BaSO₄ weighed. The samples of precipitated BaSO₄ after washing and weighing did not respond to the test of borate by burning it with a mixture of alcohol and H₂SO₄, indicating that no barium borate was precipitated.

The following tables show the data for magnetic susceptibility measurements for aqueous solutions.

TABLE I

Volume susceptibility (κ) of aq. solns. of Li₂SO₄, Na₂SO₄ & K₂SO₄ at diff. conc.

$\kappa_c = -0.789 \times 10^{-6}$ (Fe-pyrite). $\kappa_1 = -0.720 \times 10^{-6}$ (water).

No of sample.	% of salt.	θ_1 (mean) in condy. water.	θ_2 (mean) in soln.	κ_2 (vol. sns. of soln.) $\times 10^{-6}$.
<i>Li₂SO₄ solution.</i>				
1	6.23	365°.8	366°.7	-0.7236
2	9.31	385°.0	389°.4	-0.7371
3	12.10	372°.7	379°.7	-0.7482
4	16.04	375°.2	386°.3	-0.7648
<i>Na₂SO₄ solution.</i>				
1	4.73	386°.0	388°.7	-0.7304
2	7.123	378°.0	382°.0	-0.7359
3	10.156	356°.0	362°.2	-0.7461
4	14.302	363°.0	372°.4	-0.7591
5	17.987	385°.0	398°.0	-0.7710
<i>K₂SO₄ solution.</i>				
1	2.50	378°.0	379°.5	-0.7257
2	5.14	372°.5	375°.4	-0.7319
3	7.62	384°.0	388°.7	-0.7385
4	10.04	379°.5	385°.9	-0.7453

TABLE II

Determination of density.

Li_2SO_4 solution ($t=27.6^\circ$).		Na_2SO_4 solution ($t=26.0^\circ$).		K_2SO_4 solution ($t=26.3^\circ$)	
% of salt.	Density of soln.	% of salt.	Density of soln.	% of salt.	Density of soln.
6.23	1.032	4.73	1.039	2.5	1.018
9.31	1.064	7.123	1.059	5.14	1.038
12.90	1.093	10.156	1.090	7.62	1.059
16.04	1.128	14.302	1.130	10.04	1.079
		17.987	1.166		

TABLE III

Observed values of χ of aq. soln. of salts and their deviation from the calc. values.

% Composition of salt.	$\kappa_s \times 10^6$ of soln.	Density of soln.	$\chi \times 10^8$ of solution		Diff. (obs. - calc.) $\times 10^6$.
			Obs.	Calc.	
Li_2SO_4 solution (water).					
6.23	-0.7236	1.032	-0.70115	-0.6988	-0.00235
9.31	-0.7371	1.064	-0.69279	-0.6883	-0.00449
12.90	-0.74824	1.0937	-0.68413	-0.67613	-0.00800
16.04	-0.7648	1.1283	-0.67783	-0.66546	-0.01237
Na_2SO_4 solution (water).					
4.73	-0.73042	1.0392	-0.70287	-0.70189	-0.00098
7.123	-0.73594	1.0595	-0.69459	-0.69270	-0.00189
10.156	-0.74614	1.0901	-0.68446	-0.68111	-0.00335
14.302	-0.75914	1.1307	-0.67137	-0.66520	-0.00617
17.987	-0.7710	1.1666	-0.66090	-0.65112	-0.00978
K_2SO_4 solution (water).					
2.50	-0.72577	1.0188	-0.71239	-0.7120	-0.00039
5.14	-0.73194	1.0389	-0.70451	-0.7037	-0.00081
7.62	-0.73857	1.0592	-0.69728	-0.69584	-0.00144
10.04	-0.74536	1.0795	-0.69047	-0.6882	-0.00227.
χ for pure			$\text{Li}_2\text{SO}_4 = -0.38 \times 10^{-6}$		
			$\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 = -0.337$		
			$\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 = -0.403$		
			water = -0.720		

In the following tables the values of g. molecular susceptibilities (χ_m) of the three alkali halides are calculated from the additivity rule on the assumption that the value for water remains constant in solution, and the values are compared with similar values for glass systems, determined by the same method (Majumdar and Benerjee, *loc. cit.*).

TABLE IV

 Li_2SO_4 system.Normal value of salt $\times 10^6 = -41.7$.

% Salt.	Obs. χ of mixture $\times 10^6$.	* χ of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	χ_m of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	% Salt.	Obs. χ of mixture $\times 10^6$.	* χ of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	χ_m of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.
Li_2SO_4 aqueous solution.				Li_2SO_4 - $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ -glass.			
6.23	-0.70115	-0.41765	-45.91	7.02	-0.5846	-1.1541	-126.89
9.31	-0.69279	-0.42788	-47.04	9.55	-0.6759	-1.9479	-214.15
12.90	-0.68413	-0.44190	-48.58	11.50	-0.7145	-2.0452	-224.84
16.04	-0.67783	-0.45718	-50.26	12.98	-0.7643	-2.2574	-248.18

*from additivity rule.

TABLE V

 Na_2SO_4 system.Normal value of salt $\times 10^6 = -47.87$.

% Salt.	Obs. χ of mixture $\times 10^6$.	* χ of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	χ_m of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	% Salt.	Obs. χ of mixture $\times 10^6$.	* χ of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	χ_m of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.
Na_2SO_4 aqueous soln.				Na_2SO_4 - $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ -glass.			
4.73	-0.70287	-0.35776	-50.82	8.68	-0.6195	-1.4389	-204.40
7.123	-0.69459	-0.36313	-51.58	10.67	-0.6591	-1.6428	-233.37
10.156	-0.688446	-0.37004	-52.56	13.43	-0.7292	-1.9384	-275.35
14.30	-0.67137	-0.3800	-53.98	15.62	-0.7752	-2.0372	-289.38
17.98	-0.66090	-0.39130	-55.59	17.36	-0.8455	-2.2922	-325.60
				17.71	-0.8563	-2.3186	-329.35

TABLE VI

 K_2SO_4 system.Normal value of salt $\times 10^6 = -70.22$.

% Salt.	Obs. χ of mixture $\times 10^6$.	* χ of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	χ_m of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	% Salt.	Obs. χ of mixture $\times 10^6$.	* χ of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.	χ_m of salt in soln. $\times 10^6$.
K_2SO_4 -aqueous soln.				K_2SO_4 - $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ -glass.			
2.50	-0.71239	-0.41540	-72.557	5.46	-0.5580	-0.84176	-146.68
5.14	-0.70451	-0.41886	-72.986	8.64	-0.5810	-0.99759	-173.83
7.62	-0.69729	-0.42198	-73.530	11.14	-0.6070	-1.1286	-196.67
10.04	-0.69047	-0.42581	-74.196	15.38	-0.6540	-1.2724	-221.72
				18.42	-0.7580	-1.7165	-299.10

*from additivity rule.

In order to ensure that the abnormally high values of susceptibility in the case of alkali sulphates dissolved in borax-glass were not due to experimental error (these values being taken from Majumdar and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*), fresh experiments were carried out

FIG. 2

FIG. 1

with the Na_2SO_4 — $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ —glass system, in which the possibility of cationic exchange was excluded. It will be seen from the curve that it is not materially different from the corresponding one in the previous set of experiments.

TABLE VII

Na_2SO_4 — $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ —glass system.

Analysis of the glass.

Wt. of sample.	Wt. of BaSO_4 .	Wt. of Na_2SO_4 (calc.)	% of Na_2SO_4 .
0.9336 g.	0.1718 g.	0.1046 g.	11.20
0.9977	0.2390	0.1455	14.55
0.8669	0.2820	0.1717	19.80

TABLE VII (contd.)

Na₂SO₄—Na₂B₄O₇—glass system.

Magnetic susceptibility data.					
% Na ₂ SO ₄ .	θ ₁ (mean) in pyridine.	θ ₂ (mean) in diethylamine.	*κ _c × 10 ⁶ (from A. R)	Density of sample.	χ of glass × 10 ⁶ .
11.20	175°.0	147°.8	-1.693	2.547	-0.6647
14.58	195°.5	172°.0	-2.011	2.723	-0.7385
19.80	220°.0	199°.0	-2.375	2.656	-0.8947
0 (pure borax glass)	115°.0	86°.0	-1.279	2.357	-0.5427

Calculated χ_M of Na₂SO₄ in glass.

% Na ₂ SO ₄	Obs. χ of glass × 10 ⁶ .	χ of Na ₂ SO ₄ in glass (calc.) × 10 ⁶	χ _M of Na ₂ SO ₄ in glass (calc.) × 10 ⁶ .	χ _M of pure Na ₂ SO ₄ × 10 ⁶ .
11.20	-0.6647	-1.632	-231.9	
14.58	-0.7385	-1.886	-268.0	-47.87
19.80	-0.8947	-2.320	-329.7	

*“A. R.” denotes analytical results

DISCUSSION

If X be the observed mass susceptibility of the glass or aqueous solution and χ_1 and χ_2 , the values for pure borax glass or water and the salt in glass or in solution respectively, then according to the additivity rule,

$$100X = p \cdot \chi_1 + (100 - p) \cdot \chi_2.$$

Assuming the susceptibilities of borax glass and water to remain unaltered (-0.5417×10^{-6} and -0.720×10^{-6} respectively); the values for the salt in glass or in aqueous solution may be calculated. These values are shown in Tables IV-VII.

It will be seen that while in aqueous solutions the values of χ for the dissolved salts increase but little with concentration, the discrepancy between the calculated and normal values in glass solutions are far too large to be explained away by experimental error.

According to the simple theory of diamagnetism, χ is given by

$$\chi = -\frac{N \cdot e^2}{6 m c^2} \sum_n r^2,$$

where the symbols have their usual significance. Putting the numerical values of the constants, the equation reduces to

$$\chi = -2.832 \sum_n r^2 \times 10^{16}$$

As $\sum r^2$ represents the sum of the projected electronic orbits, increase in the values of χ will mean an increase in the values of $\sum r^2$, which in the case under examination would point to an increased spacing in the crystal.

The results of X-ray diffraction experiments on these systems (Majumdar and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*) reveal the existence of crystallites in the glass, but the spacings, as measured by these methods, do not seem to have undergone any appreciable change. Refraction measurements indicate on the other hand an abnormally low value of mole-refraction for the dissolved salt (Majumdar and Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **23**, 171). An abnormally small value of the latter is indicative of a very large deformation of the crystals in the glass and this fact can also not be interpreted in the light of magnetic measurements, which distinctly point to an enlargement of the lattice. The explanation of this anomaly is therefore of very great theoretical interest. That the lattice dimension of a crystal can undergo change without altering the crystal form has been hinted on theoretical grounds among others by Lennard Jones (*Z. Krist.*, 1930, **75**, 215) and others, who have calculated the extent of mutual polarising influence of different molecules (?) of the crystal on one another. But in no case is the increase more than a few per cent of the normal values. The size of the crystallite particles of the salts dispersed in the glass therefore may have something to do with the observed abnormally large values, but it cannot clearly explain the increase.

With regard to the aqueous solutions, the observed increase is in keeping with the results obtained by different workers like Veiel (*Ann. Physik*, 1935, **24**, 697), Flordal and Frivold (*ibid.*, 1935, **23**, 425), Frivold and Sogn (*ibid.*, 1935, **23**, 413) and others, who have all found a decrease in the experimental value of the susceptibility of the solutions, from their calculated values from the additivity rule which means an increase in the values of the dissolved salts over their normal values. Frivold and Sogn (*loc. cit.*) have found that the calculated values of χ of various salts in aqueous solution are greater than in alcoholic solutions. This is quite understandable if one takes into account the effects of ionisation and hydration in aqueous medium.

On the other hand, a few workers like Varadachari (*Curr. Sci.*, 1934, **3**, 249) have found no change from additivity rule in aqueous solutions of different salts including sodium sulphate and the values found are not materially different from those of the pure crystals, which is rather difficult to reconcile on theoretical grounds.

Several workers have found that the degree of subdivision of the dispersed phase in a dispersed medium affects the magnetic properties of the former. Thus, Bhatnagar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 357), Rao (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, **8**, 241) and others have found that in colloidal solutions of antimony and bismuth, the diamagnetism of the metals is actually *less* than in the metals in the massive condition. Coetz (*Phys. Rev.*, 1932, **39**, 169) from a study of graphite particles has found that above a certain size diamagnetism is independent of particle size and it decreases below a critical size (1.5×10^{-4} cm.). Prin (*Nature*, 1935, **136**, 299) has also found a smaller value of diamagnetism for colloidal solutions of metals. Thomson (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, **A**, 115,

133) on the other hand has found from electron diffraction experiments that electrolytically deposited copper has a larger spacing than ordinary copper.

In all the cases examined by us, as also in the case of noble metals like gold and platinum dispersed in borax glass (the results of which form the subject matter of separate communications) there is an abnormal increase of diamagnetism in a glass solution. Majumdar and Palit put forward an explanation concerning the role of the dielectric medium on the Coulomb and the short distance forces operating within a polar crystal lattice (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 461). According to this view, the equilibrium of a strictly polar lattice is brought about by the action of mainly two forces, the electrostatic forces between the charged ions, which follow the Coulomb law, and a short distance repulsive force, which decreases much more rapidly with the distance than the former (inversely as the seventh or the ninth power of the distance) (cf. Born and Lande, *Verhand. deuts. physikal. Ges.*, 1918, 20, 210). The potential of a single ion in the lattice (u) in a vacuum may be expressed by means of the equation,

$$u = \frac{A \cdot e^2}{d} + \frac{B}{d^n},$$

where A and B are constants called Madelung constants and d is the distance of the ion from a central ion. With the interposition of a medium of dielectric constant D , the potential will be altered to u' such that

$$u' = \frac{A \cdot e^2}{D \cdot d'} + \frac{B}{D \cdot d'^n}, \text{ where } d' > d.$$

The dielectric constant of borax glass is 7.5 (Landolt-Börnstein Tables). And hence it may be inferred that with the weakening of the electrostatic and other forces, the lattice dimensions will be increased.

There are, however, serious objections to this view. In water, which has a very high dielectric constant, the lattice is completely destroyed and the ordered arrangement obtaining in the crystal is absent in aqueous solutions as seen from the weak haloes which the latter give in X-ray diffraction experiments. But in spite of this, the departure from the additivity rule, so far as diamagnetism is concerned, is not very marked and can be explained by hydration and other effects of the ions. Why should therefore be such an abnormal increase in diamagnetism of the same salts when dispersed in a glass? This is a question which requires clarification.

The increase in diamagnetism according to some may be due to what is called Raman-Ehrenfest binding of the valency electrons, in which these are supposed to have large orbits encircling a relatively large number of atoms or ions, but the abnormal increase observed by us cannot be explained by such an assumption.

Whether a continuous lattice of the dispersed salt is formed in the glass medium also requires elucidation. According to recent theories about structure of glass due to Warren, Zachariasen and others, in glasses like borax, the periodicity obtaining in a true crystal is absent, and each boron atom is linked to three other boron atoms through three oxygen atoms forming a triangular configuration. It is also assumed that the cations like Na^+ or K^+ are joined by electrovalent linkage and take their positions

within the *hollows* of this non-periodic meshwork. It may be assumed in accordance with the theory postulated above, that when a new equilibrium results by the solidification of the melt, the Na^+ and SO_4^{2-} ions take up their positions within these hollows, conditioned by the altered electrostatic and other forces operating within the system. This, however, is also dependent on the dimensions of the hollows and on the lattice energies of the salts and of the glass meshwork.

It may be argued that the additivity rule does not hold good in such a system. This is tantamount to saying that the values of susceptibilities of the constituents in the additivity equation would not correspond to their normal values, if the value for the observed susceptibility of the glass is to fit in the equation. It is probable therefore that in such a case, the susceptibility of borax, which we have taken to be constant, actually undergoes some variation in the glass.

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